

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DISTRIBUTION PATTERNS OF FUNGI IN MOUNTAIN AND FOOTHILL SOILS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF MYCOBIOTA FORMATION

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Abstract

The presented work is dedicated to the study of structural organization, species diversity and distribution patterns of mycobiota formed in different soil types with different physico-chemical properties of Agdam and Barda regions located in the Karabakh zone of Azerbaijan. It was found that 23 types of fungi belonging to 14 genera are spread in the lands of Karabakh. It has been established that mold fungi are dominant in mountain-black soils and their number varies between $15 \cdot 10^2 - 20 \cdot 10^3$ grams. However, the low amount of organic matter in the yellow mountain-forest soils leads to a decrease in both species diversity and number content of fungi. So, the quantity of fungi is equal to $5 \cdot 10^3 - 10 \cdot 10^3$ g.

Keyword: soil types, soil composition, mycobiota, species diversity, number composition, the spread of fungi.

In addition to playing an important role in complex processes such as the exchange of water between the atmosphere and the hydrosphere and the circulation of mineral substances, the soil is considered the home of almost all living organisms. At the same time, it should be noted that the soil is the ecosystem most affected by anthropogenic influences [10;13]. Therefore, the impact mechanisms of the soil environment, whose physical and chemical properties change, on the living organisms living there change, and in some cases this effect is negative. It should be noted that the soil, especially the humus-containing fertile layer located in its upper part, is formed as a result of the activity of plant and animal organisms over many years, as well as the decomposition and mineralization of their remains after their destruction. [5;7] The quality of the soil depends on how rich it is with humus substances, as well as how it is protected from anthropogenic influences. In general, the amount of inorganic and organic substances in the soil plays an important role in determining the taxonomic structure of various living organisms, including fungi, living in the soil ecosystem [2;4].

It should be noted that the expansion of agricultural crops, including fodder crops, in the territories included in the Karabakh economic region, which has been liberated from occupation, has recently become a priority direction. Considering that the lands of Karabakh belong to the category of fertile lands and have been subjected to environmental terrorism for a long time, then the relevance of the researches conducted in this direction becomes even more important. Therefore, the study of the physico-chemical parameters of these soils was taken as the basis. It should be noted that for a long time, these lands have been regularly polluted with various toxic chemicals, including heavy metals, radionuclide compounds and other radioactive wastes, which have been discharged into the rivers [1;7]. This causes degradation of the physico-

chemical properties of the soil, which has a negative impact on the development of various living organisms living in the soil, including plants, especially on their productivity process. In this regard, it is considered appropriate to use plants that are resistant to stress factors, especially cultivated fodder plants, in such soils that are subject to pollution.

The purpose of the presented work was to study the effect of different types of soil with different physico-chemical properties located in different regions of Azerbaijan on species diversity and numerical composition of fungi.

Materials and methods

Land plots located in the mountain and foothill zones of Agdam and Barda regions were taken as the research area. As a result of the analysis of the samples taken, the genetic affiliation, physical and chemical properties, quality indicators, bioremediation properties, biology, etc. of the soil were determined. has been studied [9;12]. Soil samples for analysis were taken from mountain and foothills, yellow soils, respectively. To identify micromycetes in the mentioned soil types, first of all, soil samples are suspended and then transferred to nutrient medium in Petri dishes. treptomycin in the amount of 100 mg/l is added to the nutrient medium to fully clarify the species affiliation of the mushrooms, which almost stops the development of bacteria. The exposure period of incubation was carried out for 2 weeks at room temperature. The identified fungi are widely used in mycology due to their cultural and morphological characteristics. determined on the basis of known determinants [6;8;11]

Results obtained and their discussion

The effectiveness of the soil as an edaphic factor depends mainly on its chemical composition. It was found that there are about 60 chemical elements in the soil. In particular, the presence of ionized elements in active form has a direct effect on the soil environment.

It has been determined that the settlement of fungi in the horizontal layers of the soil, rich in plant, animal and other organic remains, is characterized by higher quantitative indicators both in terms of species diversity and number composition. Thus, it is possible to find up to 1 million microscopic fungal organisms in 1 gram of soil. It should be noted that fungi play an extremely important role in soil mineralization and humus by actively destroying the organic residues found in the soil environment with their very powerful enzyme system. It has been known that the type of soil the fungi inhabit has a direct effect on their taxonomic structure and numerical composition. In other words, the physico-chemical properties of soil types, zonal characteristics of soils, their granulometric composition, humus level, and fertility rate determine the formation of specific successions of fungi. Part of the research was conducted in black soils located in the foothills and mountainous zones of the Karabakh mountain range. It should be noted that mountain black soils do not form an independent geographical zone and are spread in local areas, especially in forest massifs and foothills. A mild climate prevails in the mountain black soil zones, and the average annual temperature ranges from 8-12°C. The amount of average annual precipitation is equal to 400-700 mm. At the same time, an average of 20-25 t/h of biomass enters the mountain black soil every year, and as a result of its decomposition and mineralization, the amount of calcium-humate com-

pounds in the soil increases. This accelerates the formation of black soils in the genesis of the soil. At the same time, it has been known that two periods are clearly visible in the black and yellow soils of the mountains and foothills. The first period coincides with July-August, when the temperature is high and the humidity is sufficient. The winter season covers the second period and is characterized by low temperature and high humidity. The mentioned favorable ecological conditions in the area intensify the process of soil formation and the accumulation of organic substances. Moreover, these conditions have a stimulating effect on the development of living organisms, including micro-mycetes, living in the soil. Thus, the stable and rich temperature, humidity, and chemical composition of the soil in the mountain black soil zones sufficiently increase the adaptation possibilities of living organisms, including fungi. Thus, the mycological analyzes conducted in mountain black soil zones show that the formed mycobiota is characterized by a fairly rich variety of species (table 1).

As it can be seen, mold fungi have a dominant position in mountain black soils. At the same time, the number content of fungi spread in mountain black soil is quite high and varies between $15 \cdot 10^3$ - $20 \cdot 10^3$ /g.

At the same time, yellow mountain forest soils were also analyzed. It was found that these lands are mainly located in the foothills and at an altitude of 50-700 m above sea level due to their geographical distribution in Barda zone.

Table 1.

Species diversity and numerical composition of fungi distributed in the soil of Karabakh zone

№	Species fungi	Mountain-black and fungi	Number composition of	Mountain yellow soil	Number composition of fungi
1	<i>Absidia cylindrospora</i>	-	15×10^3 ---- 20×10^3 CFU/g.	+	5×10^3 ---- 10×10^3 CFU/g.
2	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> Fresen	+		-	
3	<i>A.niger</i> Tiegh	+		-	
4	<i>Aspergillus niveus</i>	-		+	
5	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i> Pers Fr.	+		-	
6	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i> Kunze	+		-	
7	<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i> Schldt	+		-	
8	<i>Fusarium sambucinum</i>	+		-	
9	<i>Geomyces pannorum</i> Lk	+		-	
10	<i>Mycogone nigra</i>	-		+	
11	<i>Mortierella ramanniana</i>	+		-	
12	<i>Phielareia</i> sp.	+		-	
13	<i>Penicillium frequentans</i>	+		-	
14	<i>P.funiculosum</i> Thom	+		-	
15	<i>P.janthinellum</i> Biourge	+		-	
16	<i>Penicillium luteum</i>	-		+	
17	<i>P.thornii</i>	+		-	
18	<i>Rhizopus nigricans</i> Ehrenb.	+		-	
19	<i>Sclerotium agricola</i>	-		+	
20	<i>Talaromyces flavus</i>	-		+	
21	<i>Trichoderma koningii</i>	+		-	
22	<i>T.lignorum</i>	+		-	
23	<i>T.viride</i> Pers	-		+	

The average annual temperature is 15°C. The average annual amount of precipitation reaches 1300-1500 mm, and the top layer of the soil is constantly washed away. Therefore, the amount of Si, Ca, Mg, Al, Mn, S, P elements in these soils is very low, and the amount of organic matter is low. This leads to deterioration of the components of the mycobiota formed in the soil. *Absidia cylindrospora*, *Aspergillus niveus*, *Penicillium luteum*, *Sclerotium agricola*, *Mycogone nigra*, *Talaromyces flavus*, *Fusarium sambucinum* are found in the yellow mountain forest soils. It should be noted that not only the species diversity of fungi, but also their number content is decreasing in yellow mountain forest soils. Thus, the number of fungi in these soils is $5 \cdot 10^3 - 10 \cdot 10^3/g$.

Thus, the variety of soil types, including the difference in physico-chemical properties, biotic and abiotic factors, has a significant impact on the species diversity and numerical composition of the mycobiota formed in the soil environment, both directly and indirectly.

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